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Adaptation and Implementation of Spaced Learning Integrated with Technology (SLIT) Instructional and Students' Academic Performance in Chemistry

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Abstract

The study was on the adaptation of spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional strategy and also investigated if the implementation of SLIT instructional strategy in chemistry classroom could improve students' academic performance. A pretest, posttest, control group, quasi-experimental research design was adopted in this study. The instruments used for data collection was Chemistry Academic Performance Test (CAPT). SLIT instructional strategy was modified from Spaced learning (SL). SLIT lesson plans and CAPT were validated by two experts in Science Education. Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) formula was used to test internal consistency of CAPT which yielded a reliability value of 0.91. The population of the study was made up of 5,127 Senior Secondary 2 students offering chemistry in the 21-government approved secondary schools in the Aldo-Kola Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria. A total of 124 students was purposively sampled from 4 schools out of 47 schools in the study area. Two research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the null hypotheses were tested using results from Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The study revealed that there is a significant difference between SLIT instructional strategy and discussion method of teaching in favour of SLIT instructional strategy [$F_{1, 123} = 98.765, p < 0.05$]. It was found that no significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry using SLIT instructional strategy [$F_{1, 60} = 3.420, P > 0.05$]. It was revealed that there is no significant interaction effect of treatments and gender on the mean academic performance scores of students in Chemistry [$F_{1, 123} = .129, P > 0.050$]. It was recommended among others that since SLIT instructional strategy was found to be effective Strategy for improving students' academic performance irrespective of gender; Chemistry teachers should adopt the use of spaced learning integrated with technology.

Keywords: Spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional strategy, Students' Academic Performance and Chemistry

Introduction

Chemistry is an experimental science that systematically studies the composition, chemical and physical properties and activities of substances or elementary forms of matter (Ajayi, 2019). For a nation to develop in science and technology, the teaching and learning of chemistry need to be continually assessed and improved

(Ajayi & Ogbeba, 2017). Therefore, it is pertinent that performances in chemistry and in science generally should be of high levels. However, this seems not be the case in Nigeria because students' academic performance has not been encouraging in chemistry for couples of subsequent years (WAEC, 2020). Adamu (2016) opines that, the main objective of teaching chemistry in

senior secondary schools is to equip students with scientific methods, reasoning and to prepare students for tertiary institution in chemistry related courses. By implication, with the rapid science and technological development, there is need for students to be well equip with necessary scientific skills to live effectively. To achieve this, there is need for chemistry to be proper taught in senior secondary schools.

Students need to be trained to think in more purposive ways to organize their environment more systematically and view the world with more meaning (Ajayi, 2017). Teaching of chemistry is planned process of transformation of knowledge into principles and the required planned action (experimentation) for understanding. The chemistry teacher tries to describe, elucidate and explain concepts and solve problems of relevance. By implication, the students' curiosity needs to be nurtured and to facilitate teacher to enable the students to engage in acquiring methods and processes that nurtures their retention, curiosity, problem solving and creativity, there is need to equip teachers with innovative teaching strategies that have the potentials to do so. The researchers opine that, the teaching of chemistry needs to be more constructive and the teacher needs to be facilitative in order that the students engage scientific inquiry, do experiments and discuss concepts in chemistry to refine ones understanding of the nature of chemistry and its application in life. The poor academic performance of students in chemistry in external examination has been a major concern to researchers.

Studies by Ogbeba, Enemarie, and Ajayi (2019); Achor Ajayi, Ikwu and Onyeche (2020); Ajayi, Achor and Otor (2020) revealed that poor teaching methods, poor performance in basic science in Basic Education level, assessment pattern, teacher content knowledge, truancy, and peer pressure are some of the causes of

students' poor performance. The poor academic performance is attested to in the Chemistry result of students in Nigeria and Taraba State in particular in the West African Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations (WASSCE) May/June, 2012 to 2022. However, the West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiners' report (2020/2021) on Chemistry result indicates that students are weak in Chemistry due to the fact that candidates do not familiarize themselves with the required syllabus; and teachers do not employ effective instructional methods. Thus, ineffective teaching method is the most prominent among the identified causes of students' poor academic performance in chemistry. By implication, poor teaching method invariably translates to students' poor academic performance.

Most Nigerian chemistry teachers use discussion method most frequently in their classrooms which usually degenerate into mere talk and may be monopolized by few individuals. Based on this, the nation's quest for science and technology advancement to produce the right calibre of citizens equipped with the right type of scientific and technological skills, and attitudes for national adaptation will become a mirage, if effective modality is not put in place to incorporate innovative methods that promote meaningful learning, thus, there is needs to ensure that chemistry is properly taught using 21st century innovative teaching strategies. Thus, the researchers adapted spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional strategy.

Spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional strategy was adapted from spaced learning strategy by the researchers to foster students' interaction and engagement using technology tools. It involves integrating simple technology tools such as PowerPoints presentations, multimedia (multimedia platforms such YouTube, Glogster, Micro-Duino, Flipgrid,

etcetera can also be used) or video mini-lesson, podcasts, classroom kit, Nearpod and games (computer gamified packages) to space learning strategy. Scientists have tried to understand long-term memory (LTM) processes through a variety of strategies including using repeated and spaced stimuli (Pavlov, 2010). Spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional strategy is a learning strategy in which highly condensed learning content is repeated two or three times with the use of technological tools, with two 5-10 minutes breaks during which distractor activities such as physical activities are performed by the students. In (SLIT) instructional strategy, lessons are usually delivered using a PowerPoint presentation, so a classroom with a projector is required together with a computer. Spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional strategy involves a lesson consisting of two to three inputs spaced by two 5-10 minutes break which students spend doing physical activities such as ball games, juggling and practice paper cutting into different shapes. Spaced learning strategy was first designed and developed by Paul Kelley in 2005 at Monk-Seaton High School in North-East England (Douglas, 2005). It is a method of embedding information in our long-term memory through repetition. This process of rapid structured repetition, separated by short breaks, embeds the information in the long-term memory and enhanced conceptual understanding. The difference between spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional strategy and spaced learning strategy is that, SLIT instructional strategy emphasizes on integrating technology in classroom.

Development of Spaced Learning Integrated with Technology (SLIT)

Technology plays a large role in providing a more engaged learning environment, boosts collaboration and support learning. The use of technology

makes the teaching process objective, clear, simple, interesting, engaging and effective. Thus, the researchers developed an eight-step format for spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional package as follows;

Step 1: Set Induction

Teacher Activity; Teacher to

Arouse students' interest by making clear to the students the objectives of the day's study and making clear to them the importance of the subject matter and its relevance to daily life.

- Give the students a resume of what is to be taught, after asking them a few questions to probe into their prior knowledge, teacher then explains what the concept/ topic to be taught is all about.

Students' Activity; students

- Answer the questions orally.
- Students jot down some points as the teacher speaks. They are also allowed to ask questions.

Step 2: Presentation of Lesson Contents using Technology Tools

Teacher Activity; Teacher to

- Present the lesson contents (information, materials, facts, and skills) using technological tools such as PowerPoint, video presentations or video mini-lesson, podcasts, YouTube, and games (computer gamified packages) and so on.
- engage students in hands-on activities during presentation using appropriate technological tool(s)
- A few minutes of full-class discussion will provide the students on the concept to be taught.
- Explain the lesson contents in detail to the students using appropriate technological tools.

Students' Activity; Students to

- Listen or watch and jot down some points as the teacher makes presentations.

- Engage in hands-on activities.
- They are allowed to ask questions for clarification.

Step 3: Distractor activities I (Break)

Teacher Activity; Teacher to

Give distractor activities (The breaks are 5-10 minutes long because this time period is enough to allow the pathway created to be 'rested' before the next stimulation or in order to strengthen the neutral pathways recording the information or skills.

- Supervise students as they engage in distractor activities.

Students' Activity; Students to

- The students proceed on breaks.
- They are involved in distractor activities.

Step 4: Recall of Lesson Contents Presented in Step 2

Teacher Activity;

- ask challenging question(s) that can engage the students in critical thinking to recall the concepts earlier presented.
- Supervise students' activities if the answers to the challenges question(s) involve hands-on activities.

Students' Activity;

- Answer the question asked by the teacher.
- Undertake the activities (discrepant events) which are designed to provide answers to the challenging questions.

Step 5: Representation of Lesson Contents

Teacher Activity; Teacher to

- Represent the lesson contents in a slightly different technology enhanced ways or through classroom discussion. However, students may be allowed to solve problems relating to the contents at this stage.
- Explain the lesson contents in detail to the students using relatedly different style.

Students' Activity; Students to

- Listen or watch and jot down some points as the teacher makes presentations.
- They are allowed to ask questions for clarification.

Step 6: Distractor activities II (Break)

Teacher Activity; Teacher to

- Give distractor activities (The distractor activities (such as juggling and ball games) during the break are also different as this minimizes the danger of disrupting the pathways being formed)
- Supervise students as they engage in distractor activities.

Students' Activity; Students to

- The students proceed on breaks.
- They are involved in distractor activities.

Step 7: Recall of Lesson Contents Represented in Step 5

Teacher Activity; Teacher to

- Ask memory refreshing questions that will enable students to recall what they have learnt.
- Make further clarification when necessary.

Students' Activity; Students to

- Answer the question asked by the teacher.

Step 8: Evaluation

Teacher Activity; Teacher to

- Engage students in tasks that involves application of the knowledge or skills learnt and confirming the facts.
- Design diagnostic tests to assess recall and understanding.
- Collect the tests.
- Review it to assess their understanding.
- Summarize the lesson for more understanding by the students.

Students' Activity; Students to

- Carry out tasks, applying the knowledge or skills.

- Students give answers to the questions asked by the teacher.
- Listen attentively to the teacher.

With a view to improving chemistry instructions, the researchers opine that, since spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional strategy is grounded in constructivist framework, it is very likely that chemistry could be simplified and made easier to understand as students go through SLIT teaching/learning steps or phases. Thus, the study investigated if the implementation of the SLIT instructional strategy in chemistry classroom could improve students' academic performance.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate if the implementation of spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional strategy can enhance students' academic performance in Chemistry. Specifically, the study;

1. Find out the effect of SLIT instructional strategy on students' academic performance in Chemistry.
2. Investigate the difference in effect of SLIT instructional strategy between male and female students' academic performance in Chemistry.
3. Investigate the interaction effect between strategies and gender on students' academic performance in Chemistry.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean academic performance between students taught Chemistry using SLIT instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method?
2. What is the difference in the mean academic performance between male and female students taught Chemistry using SLIT instructional strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance between students taught Chemistry using SLIT instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance between male and female students taught Chemistry using SLIT instructional strategy.
3. There is no significant interaction effect of treatments and gender on the mean academic performance scores of students in Chemistry.

Methods

The study employed pre-test, post-test quasi experimental design. The study area was Aldo-Kola Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria. The population of the study was made up of 5,127 Senior Secondary 2 students in the 21-government approved secondary schools. A sample of 124 students were purposively sampled from 4 schools out of 21 schools in the study area. One instrument known as Chemistry Academic performance Test (CAPT) was used to collect data for this study. CAPT is a researcher made instrument that contains two sections. Section A contains bio-data information of the respondents, while section B contains 40 multi-choice objective items questions which respondents are expected to provide the correct answer by ticking the correct options (A-D). Chemistry Academic performance Test (CAPT) was validated by three experts of Science Education and two experts in Measurement and Evaluation all from Taraba State University, Jalingo. Corrections and suggestions arising from these experts were used to review the instrument before it was used. Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) was used to obtain the

CAPT reliability, which yielded a coefficient value of 0.91.

The conduct of the study took place during the normal school lesson periods. The normal time-table of the schools for the study were followed. Before the commencement of the actual treatment, the researcher used one week for the training of the Chemistry teachers who served as research assistants. The training programme was to ensure the homogeneity of instructional situation across all groups. The training for the experimental group only differs from that of the control group by the use of SLIT instructional strategy. The sample was divided into two groups namely; experimental and control group. During lessons, the experimental group was taught Chemistry using SLIT instructional strategy in line with lessons procedure prepared by the researcher while the control group was taught the same Chemistry topics using the discussion lesson notes which lasted for four weeks. The study covers three sub-topics under Chemistry which includes alkane, alkene, and ethanol and redox reaction selected from the SS2 scheme of work. The choice of the sub-topics was to help students overcome the difficulties associated with

academic performance in Chemistry as one of the areas that stand out as problem areas to Chemistry students in the report by the Chief Examiner's for West African Examination Council (2019/2020). Chemistry Academic performance Test (CAPT) was administered as pre-test by the researcher with the assistance of the sampled schools Chemistry teachers. This lasted for one week before actual teaching commences. At the end of these periods, the post-CAPT was administered which lasted for one week. The descriptive statistics of Mean and standard deviation were used to answer to the research questions while the inferential statistics of ANCOVA was used to test the null hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean academic performance between students taught Chemistry using SLIT instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method? The answer to research question one is contained in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Academic Performance and Standard Deviation Scores of Students using SLIT instructional strategy and Discussion Method

Group	N	PRE- CAPT		POST- CAPT		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
SLIT Strategy	60	8.36	1.10	20.54	1.31	12.18
Discussion	64	8.34	1.13	13.02	1.22	4.68
Mean difference		0.02		7.52		7.50

The results in Table 1 reveal that, the pre-test mean scores for SLIT instructional strategy and discussion groups are 8.36 and 8.34 respectively with their standard deviation scores of 1.10 and 1.13 respectively. The post-test mean scores accordingly were 20.54 and 13.02 with their standard deviation scores of 1.31 and 1.22 respectively.

The overall difference between the SLIT strategy and discussion groups was 7.50 in favour of SLIT group. This implies that the learners in SLIT instructional strategy had higher academic performance than their counterpart in discussion group.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the mean academic performance between male and female students taught Chemistry using

SLIT instructional strategy? The answer to research question two is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Mean Academic Performance and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Chemistry using SLIT Strategy

Group	Gender	N	PRE- CAPT		POST- CAPT		Mean Gain within Gender
			\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
SLIT Strategy	Male	34	7.21	1.54	17.91	5.15	17.98
	Female	26	7.15	1.56	17.44	5.02	17.46
Mean diff. between Gender			0.06		0.47		0.41

Table 2 reveals the mean academic performance and standard deviation scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using SLIT instructional strategy. The data in Table 2 show that the pre-test mean scores for male and female students were 7.21 and 7.15 with standard deviation scores of 1.54 and 1.56 respectively while the post-test mean scores were 17.91 and 17.44 with standard deviation scores of 5.15 and 5.02 respectively. The mean difference of both sexes was 0.41. This difference

though small is in favour of the male students. This implies that male students achieved slightly higher than their female counterparts in SLIT Strategy class.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance between students taught Chemistry using SLIT strategy and those taught using discussion method.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance for Academic Performance Scores of Students taught using SLIT strategy and Discussion Method

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	3493.193 ^a	4	1422.253	26.774	.000	.437
Intercept	4556.668	1	4556.668	84.009	.000	.408
TPr ^{CPT}	79.347	1	79.347	1.962	.154	.017
Group	5535.021	1	5535.021	98.765	.000	.792
Gender	22.027	1	22.027	.487	.401	.002
Group * Gender	.341	1	.341	.119	.503	.000
Error	6529.110	120	5.621			
Total	94124.030	123				
Corrected Total	13613.303	122				

a. R squared = .127 (Adjusted R Squared= .123)

ANCOVA Test result in Table 3 reveals that there is a significant difference between the mean performance of students in SLIT instructional strategy and discussion method of teaching in favour of SLIT

Strategy [$F_{1, 123}=98.765, p<0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that SLIT was highly effective than discussion method in improving students' academic performance in chemistry.

Meanwhile, the effect size of 0.792 as shown by the corresponding partial eta squared value is considered as large effect size. This implies that, 79.2% of the variance in the academic performance scores among the groups was explained by the treatments. Hence, the difference in

Table 4: ANCOVA Result for Academic Performance of Male and Female Students Taught Chemistry using SLIT Strategy

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	15.224 ^a	2	7.612	.284	.753	.006
Intercept	6811.882	1	6811.882	254.507	.000	.722
TPr ^{CPT}	3.655	1	3.655	.137	.713	.001
Gender	19.431	1	19.431	3.420	.239	.002
Error	2622.974	58	26.765			
Total	81319.008	60				
Corrected Total	2638.198	59				

a. R squared = .026 (Adjusted R Squared= -.022)

ANCOVA Test result in Table 4 reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry using SLIT Strategy $F_{1, 60} = 3.420, P > 0.05$. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This means that SLIT Strategy enhanced both male and female students' academic performance in Chemistry. Meanwhile, the effect size of 0.002 is considered as very small. This implies that, only 0.2% of the difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry was explained by SLIT Strategy. Hence, the difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry using SLIT Strategy has small statistical effect size.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant interaction effect of treatments and gender on the mean academic performance scores of students in Chemistry.

The data analysis of Table 3 is used to explain hypothesis 3. The table presents the ANCOVA for academic performance of

the academic performance among the groups has a large statistical effect size.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance between male and female students taught Chemistry using SLIT instructional strategy.

students taught Chemistry using SLIT strategy and discussion method (DM). The table also presents the interaction effect of instructional strategies and gender. The data in Table 3 reveals that there is no significant interaction effect of treatments and gender on the mean academic performance scores of students in Chemistry [$F_{1, 123} = .119, P > 0.050$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. Meanwhile, the effect size was 0.000 as indicated by the corresponding partial eta squared value which is considered as small effect size. This implies that, only 0.0% of the interaction in the academic performance scores among groups was explained by treatments and gender. Hence, the strategies do not interact with gender to influence performance and there was no contribution to significance from the effect size

Discussion

This research was on adaptation of spaced learning integrated with technology (SLIT) instructional strategy to design chemistry lesson plans and also

investigated if the implementation of SLIT instructional strategy in chemistry classroom could enhance students' academic performance in Chemistry. Arising from the failure to produce the desired results in terms of students' academic performance in chemistry due to ineffective teaching methods used by teachers, the researchers deemed it fit to develop chemistry lesson plans using SLIT strategy phases and also investigated its effectiveness. The researchers opined that, SLIT instructional strategy developed has the potential to help students tap into exploration as they attempt to solve a problem.

The finding of the study revealed that students taught Chemistry using SLIT performed significantly higher than their counterparts taught using discussion method. Though, there is scarcity of study on SLIT strategy, this finding agrees with Usmanu and Dawani (2013) who found that students taught business administration using spaced teaching approach had higher performance than those taught using conventional teaching method. Similarly, this is in line with Aminu (2015), and Adamu (2016) findings that students improved significantly in their achievement in Physics and Algebra respectively when taught using spaced teaching approach compared to those taught using lecture method. The likely explanation for this outcome may also be connected to the fact that the use of spaced teaching approach provides the opportunity for students to revisit highly condensed information presented in separate time intervals with the purpose of facilitating the storage of this information in the long-term memory. Unlike, when compared to discussion method that only promotes passive learning. Therefore, Using SLIT strategy will make students begin to appreciate Chemistry.

The study also revealed that male students achieved slightly higher than their

female counterparts using SLIT strategy but ANCOVA test shows that the difference was no significant. This implies that, the difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry using SLIT Strategy was not statistically significant. This implies that SLIT strategy improved both male and female students' academic performance in Chemistry. Though, there was scarcity of previous study on SLIT in relation to students' gender. This finding agrees with Usmanu and Dawani (2013) who found that spaced teaching approach facilitated students' performance in business administration regardless of gender in Iqra University, Pakistan. Similarly, this is also in line with Adamu (2016) findings that both male and female students improved significantly in their attitude in Algebra using spaced teaching strategy. However, the finding contradicts the finding of Aminu (2015) who found that female students had higher achievement than their male counterparts in Physics using spaced teaching approach. Therefore, if SLIT strategy is implemented in classroom, it will enable male and female students to understand how concepts and processes are meaningfully learnt.

The interaction effect between strategies and gender on the academic performance of students in Chemistry is very minimal but ANCOVA test shows that the interaction effect was not significant. Therefore, there is no main effect of treatment on gender. This is in line with Olagunju and Babayemi (2014); Agamber (2021) who found that there was no significant interaction between approaches and gender on interest of students in Biology and Ecology respectively. Therefore, there is no need for separation of instructional strategy for male and female students, since either SLIT instructional strategy could be used successfully for the two groups.

Conclusion

SLIT instructional strategy is more effective in improving students' academic performance in Chemistry than discussion method. By implication, this affirmed that students' academic performance in chemistry depend on the instructional strategies. It is also evident from the findings of this study that SLIT can foster students' academic performance irrespective of gender differences. Thus, SLIT is significantly a very useful strategy for effective learning and teaching of Chemistry. Based on this the following recommendations are made:

1. Chemistry teachers should adopt SLIT instructional strategy to design or develop chemistry instructions, since it was found to be an effective strategy in improving students' academic performances in Chemistry.
2. Workshops should be organised through professional bodies such as Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) to sensitize Chemistry teachers with a view to improving their skills and experiences on the usage of instructional strategy aimed at developing students' academic performances in Chemistry.

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Appendix

Sample of SLIT Instructional Strategy Lesson Plan

School:	As Applicable
Subject:	Chemistry
Specific Topic:	Alkenes
Class:	SS II
Number in class:	As Applicable
Average Age:	16 Years
Sex:	Mixed
Time:	80 minutes
Date:	As Applicable

Behavioural objectives: By the end of the lesson students should be able to:

1. define the term alkenes and write general formula of alkenes;
2. mention at least four physical properties of ethene;
3. draw the structure of ethene accurately;
4. clearly describe the chemical properties of ethene;
5. correctly carryout the laboratory preparation of ethene; and
6. mention at least four uses of ethene.

Instructional Materials: beakers, measuring cylinder, ethyne, ethanol (C₂H₅OH), conc.H₂SO₄, nickel catalyst, computer sets, projector, video mini-lesson, podcasts, and games (computer gamified packages)

Previous knowledge: Students have studied alkanes

Instructional Procedure/Presentation

Content Development	Time (mins)	Teacher's activities	Students' activities
Step 1 Set Induction	5	<p>Arouses students' interest and motivates them to learn. Tell students the objectives of the lesson. Probes into students' prior knowledge through questions such as: what are alkanes? What are alkenes?</p> <p>Makes known to the students the teaching technique and its demand on them</p> <p>Explains that the simpler member of alkene family is ethene (C₂H₄) and other members are propene (C₃H₆), butene (C₄H₈), pentene (C₅H₁₀), hexene (C₆H₁₂).</p>	<p>Students answer the questions asked by the teacher</p> <p>Expected answers: Alkanes are saturated hydrocarbons that is to say compounds of carbon and hydrogen which only have single, covalent, bonds holding the atoms together. With general molecular formula C_nH_{2n+2} and functional group of C-C.</p>
Step 2 Presentation of Lesson Contents using Technology Tool(s)	20	<p>Explain what is ethene, the preparation and physical properties of ethene with the aid PowerPoint presentation containing a mini-video designed by the teacher to stimulate students' conceptual understanding, engagement and interest.</p> <p>(The mini-video can also be sources from any multimedia platform such as YouTube or Glogster). For instance, for what is ethene? Check the following 2 minutes mini-video: https://youtu.be/GIWx1A_s72w</p> <p>For preparation and physical properties of ethene. Check the following 5 minutes mini-video: https://youtube.com/watch?v=0xLFGvN7bO0&feature=share</p> <p>Asks the students to draw the structure of ethene Explain the chemical properties of ethene and importance of ethene with the aid PowerPoint presentation containing a mini-video</p>	<p>While listening and watching the mini-video, students jot down points and also take note of the experiment observations and results.</p> <p>They are allowed to ask questions for clarification.</p> <p>Expected answers The structure of ethene is as follows:</p>
Step 3 Distractor activities 1 (Break)	10	<p>Give distractor activities (The breaks are 5-10 minutes long because this time period is enough to allow the pathway created to be 'rested' before the next stimulation or in order to strengthen the neural pathways recording the information or skills. Supervise students as they</p>	<p>The students proceed on breaks</p> <p>They are involved in distractor activities</p>

		engage in distractor activities	
Step 4 Recall of Lesson Contents Presented in Step 2	10	After the presentation, ask the students questions related to preparation and physical properties of ethene using puzzles or computer gamified package.	Answer the question asked by the teacher Undertake the activities (discrepant events) which are designed to provide answers to the challenging questions.
Step 5 Representation of Lesson Contents	15	Represent the same lesson contents in a slightly different way. For instance, through laboratory demonstration or classroom discussion or using other forms of technological tool(s). However, students may be allowed to solve problems relating to the contents at this stage	Listen or watch and jot down some points as the teacher makes presentations. They are allowed to ask questions for clarification
Step 6 Distractor activities II (Break)	10	Give distractor activities (The distractor activities (such as juggling and ball games) during the break are also different as this minimizes the danger of disrupting the pathways being formed) Supervise students as they engage in distractor activities	The students proceed on breaks. They are involved in distractor activities
Step 7 Recall of Lesson Contents Represented in Step 5	5	Ask memory refreshing questions that will enable students to recall what they have learnt. Ask question such as; i. What is the importance of ethene ii. mention the chemical properties of ethene Make further clarification when necessary Expected students' answers: Ethene is extremely important in the manufacture of plastic. All plastics are in some way related to alkene. Ethene is used as fuel and illuminant. Ethene is used in the manufacture of glycerol and detergent.	Answer the question asked by the teacher
Step 8 Evaluation	5	Engage students in tasks or questions that involves application of the knowledge or skills learnt and confirming the facts. Summarize the lesson for more understanding by the students	Students give answers to the questions asked by the teacher. Listen attentively to the teacher
	80		